

DATA SCARCITY IN LOW-RESOURCE AND ENDANGERED LANGUAGES

► **Neural Machine Translation** models are data hungry and, as a result, they are biased toward the 20 languages that are spoken by 50% of the world's population, while most of the remaining languages are spoken by less than a thousand people.

► **Data Scarcity** is a huge issue in the case of Low-Resourced and Endangered languages. There are about 7000 currently spoken languages but more than half of them are estimated to be severely endangered or dead by the year 2100 [1].

► **The Development** of a translation system helps the preservation and revitalization of endangered languages as well as increase the economic opportunities for the speaking minorities.

LEARNING FROM WRONG PREDICTIONS

- To address the problem of data shortage, we develop a method that learns from unaligned sentences, that is, we couple source sentences to the incorrect sentences (hence wrong predictions). In this way, we can draw samples from a dataset of size $|D|^2$ where $|D|$ denotes the initial dataset size.
- We introduce the concept of Keytokens and the USKI pre-training method that trains the models on a special set of tokens increasing the model's overall performance and the robustness against incorrect predictions in auto-regressive decoding.

Keytokens

Given two arbitrary samples in source and target language $X_i \in D_{L_X}$ and $Y_j \in D_{L_Y}$ we define a *KeyToken* as a matching token between two different sentences Y_j and Y_i in the target language. We denote with $\mathbb{K}_{i,j}$ the set of all keytokens between the target Y_i and Y_j , formally $K_{i,j} = Y_i \cap Y_j$.

For instance, assuming the target sentences of two generic unaligned pairs being: $Y_i = \{ 'a', 'piece', 'of', 'furniture', 'with', 'four', 'legs', 'used', 'for', 'eating' \}$ and $Y_j = \{ 'a', 'dog', 'is', 'eating', 'a', 'piece', 'of', 'chicken' \}$. KeyTokens $K_{i,j}$ denote a set of tokens contained in both the correct translation Y_i and the arbitrary one Y_j : $K_{i,j} = \{ 'a', 'piece', 'eating', 'of' \}$.

USKI

Using the concept of Keytokens we introduce the Unaligned Sentences Keytokens Pre-training. Given a training sample $(X_i, Y_j) \subset (X_i, Y_i, X_j, Y_j)$, $(X_i, Y_i, X_j, Y_j) \in \tilde{D}$ the Pre-Training minimizes the following formula:

$$-\sum_t \mathbb{1}(g_t) \cdot \log(p_\theta(y_t = g_t | y_{1:t-1}, X_i)) \cdot w(g_t) \quad (1)$$

where y_1, \dots, y_T are tokens in the prediction, g_1, \dots, g_T are

the ground-truth tokens of Y_j and $\mathbb{1} : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $w : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are functions that map tokens from the vocabulary V to \mathbb{R} . $\mathbb{1}$ is described by the following equations:

$$\begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } g_t \in \mathbb{K}_{i,j} \\ 0 & \text{if } g_t \notin \mathbb{K}_{i,j} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where w denotes the Inverse-Document-Frequency (IDF) function. To compute the IDF term $w(g)$, $g \in V$ we first define the un-normalized version $\tilde{w}(g)$:

$$\tilde{w}(g) = \log\left(\frac{|D_{L_X, L_Y}| \cdot \alpha}{\max(1, \phi(g))}\right) \quad (3)$$

where α is a corpus size correction coefficient and $\phi : V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a function that counts the number of occurrences of g in the target training set:

$$f(g) = \sum_z |D_{L_Y}| \min(1, c_{gz}) \quad (4)$$

where c_{gz} is the number of occurrences of g in the sequence Y_z . The term $w(g)$ is then defined as:

$$w(g) = \frac{\tilde{w}(g)}{\sum_{q \in V} \tilde{w}(q)} + \gamma \quad (5)$$

where γ is an offset weight, and together with α they are configurable parameters.

The IDF term w is introduced to prevent the model from focusing on function words of the language L_Y which are the most likely words to co-occur in two arbitrary sentences.

Complete Training procedure

The complete training procedure consists of:

- USKI Pre-Training.** First, we train the model, in this case, the vanilla Transformer, on the USKI pre-training;
- Traditional XE training.** We then fine-tune the model on the traditional training cross-entropy loss.

We select the Selkup-Russian, Evenki-Russian, Griko-Italian, Uzbek-English and Wolof-Ukrainian language pairs. Additionally, since training on the complete set of un-aligned pairs, we limit ourselves to roughly 13% of the whole dataset, comprised of the most valuable pairs according to our loss formulation. That is, we filter out the pairs with a target Intersection Over Union (or Keytokens cardinality ratio) lower than 10%, which is the majority of the dataset.

PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Task	Baseline	w/ USKI	$\delta \uparrow$
Sel→Ru	7.05±0.50	8.19±0.38	1.14
Sel←Ru	4.15±0.45	5.98±0.34	1.83
Ev→Ru	6.58±0.48	7.26±0.39	0.68
Ev←Ru	7.36±0.85	8.65±0.90	1.29
Gk→It	5.91±0.10	6.23±0.10	0.32
Gk←It	4.43±0.07	5.58±0.17	1.15
Uz→En	18.82±0.74	19.94±0.38	1.12
Uz←En	18.40±0.43	19.07±0.38	0.67
Wol→Uk	4.60±0.13	5.00±0.12	0.40
Wol←Uk	8.25±0.05	8.62±0.14	0.37

The third column of the Table reports the scores of the model when our proposed pre-training is applied before the standard translation training. The maximum improvement of 1.83 BLEU is observed in the case of Ru ← Sel, whereas the lowest one, of 0.37 BLEU, is showcased in the Wol ← Uk case. An average improvement of 0.9 BLEU can be appreciated. Although it is not very high, it is good considering the magnitude of the initial value and the experimental setup.

KEYTOKENS ACCURACY, GRANULARITY AND MBART

Models pre-trained on USKI showcase, as expected, a higher accuracy over the tokens that were valued the most, according to the IDF-term, during the Keytokens pre-training.

Task	Baseline	w/ USKI	mBART
Sel→Ru	7.05	8.19	18.50
Ev→Ru	6.58	7.26	26.03
Gk→It	5.91	6.23	9.12
Uz→En	18.82	19.94	20.88
Wol→Uk	4.69	5.00	6.24

Our proposal is less performant compared to mBART. However, the results are satisfying given the poor model setup and training premises.

Vocab size	Baseline	w/ USKI	$\delta \uparrow$
4356	19.07	19.64	0.57
7983	19.68	20.08	0.40
11385	19.49	19.95	0.46
13901	20.06	20.29	0.23

USKI effectiveness is affected by the subword tokenization.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sallabank J. and Austin P. K. 2011. Endangered Languages. The SAGE Handbook of Sociolinguistics. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

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